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Spectrophotometric studies of V(IV) 4-Hydroxy 3-formylazobenzene and Mg(II) and Ni(II) Sodium 4-Hydroxy 3-formylazobenzene 4'-Sulphonate Complexes

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IN continuation of our previous communication¹⁷ we now report the spectrophotometric studies of the complexes of V(IV) with 4-hydroxy 3-formylazobenzene (HFB) and Ni(II) and Mg(II) with sodium 4-hydroxy 3-formylazobenzene 4'-sulphonate (SHFBS).

The synthesis of the ligand and their properties have been described in the previous communication¹.

A Hilger and Watts (England) spectrophotometer was used for absorption measurements.

The studies with SHFBS were carried out in aqueous medium while those with HFB in 42% (V/V) alcohol-water mixture.

The λ_{max} of the HFB was found at 430 nm while that of the V(IV) complex was found at 470 nm (at pH 5 to 6) and of SHFBS was found at 590 nm and Mg(II) and Ni(II) complexes were found at 530 nm (at pH 6.0 to 8.0). Hence these wave lengths were chosen to study stoichiometry of the components by Job's continuous variation, mole ratio and slope ratio methods. The validity of Beer's law was seen. The absorbance measurements were carried out after 24 hrs of equilibration. The colour did not fade even after one week. The pH of the solutions were adjusted at the required level by using different buffer solutions. The absorbance measurements were carried out between 350 to 950 nm at 30°.

In order to derive the composition of the complex the following methods were used :

- 1) Job's method² using equimolar metal and ligand solutions ;
- 2) Mole Ratio Method³ ;
- 3) Slope Ratio Method⁴.

All the solutions were adjusted to the same solvent composition in the case of the V(IV)-HFB complex.

The stability constants were calculated from the absorbance data using the mole ratio method.

The values of 'a' for V(IV)-HFB, Mg(II)-SHFBS and Ni(II)-SHFBS complexes were calculated to be 0.061, 0.34 and 0.35 respectively using the above values of 'a' and instability and the stability constants have been calculated.

The standard free energy of formation of the complexes have been calculated using the relation $\Delta F = -RT \ln K$.

V(IV), Mg(II) and Ni(II) were found to form 1:2 complexes. The log K values for the V(IV)-HFB, Mg(II)-SHFBS and Ni(II)-SHFBS chelates were calculated to be 8.4352, 6.0207 and 5.9767 respectively.

The ΔF values for these complexes were found to be -11.7722, -8.4026 and -8.3393 K.Cals/mole respectively at 30°.

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Studies on the Clay Mineralogy of Aligarh Soil Profiles

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ALIGARH district (latitude 28° north and 78° east) is an important soil area among the districts of Uttar Pradesh. It has large tracts of alkaline

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and saline lands and can be considered as representative of the alluvium of the western region. Though a considerable amount of information is available on the physico-chemical characteristics of its soils and recent studies^{1,2} provide some useful data on the clay mineral content of one of its surface samples, little information is available on the detailed mineralogical make up of its various soil types on a profile basis. A study of clay minerals is important because of their chemical reactivity which often affects plant nutritional status, soil water holding capacity, soil development and engineering behaviour. Such studies are of added importance in case of Aligarh as it is the only model district selected in Uttar Pradesh for the Intensive Agriculture Development Programme.

The chief objective of this investigation was to determine the mineralogical content of six of the typical profiles of the district as revealed by studies involving chemical and X-ray analyses.

Experimental

Soil profiles were exposed in the six typical areas of the district as indicated in the Soil Survey Records³ and the thirty two samples were collected from the various depths of the representative profiles. The representative nature of the surface samples was checked by the determination and comparison of the mechanical composition, exchangeable cations

and soluble salts. Less than 2 micron clay was separated from the various soil samples by treatment with hydrogen peroxide and dispersion with sodium oxalate followed by sedimentation and centrifugation. For the total elemental analysis, the clay fractions were subjected to estimation for silicon, aluminium and iron by the semi-microchemical method of Corey and Jackson⁴. Total calcium plus magnesium were determined in the solution (left after the removal of Fe, Al and Si) by versene titration and calcium alone by using murexide and eriochrome black T as indicator following HF treatment. Sodium and potassium were estimated by flame photometry. Blanks were carried out as control for impurities of reagents and contamination from glassware.

The X-ray diffractometric studies of the clays were made in their sodium form. The X-ray patterns observed corresponded to the lattice spacings of minerals illite, chlorite, quartz and feldspar as per ASTM Card Nos. 9-343, 9-334, 13-29, 5-0490 and 10-359 respectively.

Results and Discussion

The results of X-ray analysis are given in Table 1. The first two columns list the names of the predominant minerals occurring in the soils in the decreasing order of their abundance. Minerals where

TABLE 1—CLAY MINERALOGICAL COMPOSITION OF THE SOIL PROFILES.

Soil type	Depth in cms	Clay minerals detected in order of abundance				
		1 > 15%	2 > 10%	3 > 5%	4 about 5%	5 about 5%
I. Ganga Khadir	0—28	—	Illite	Quartz	Chlorite	Feldspar
	28—38	Illite	Quartz	—	Chlorite	Feldspar
	38—43	Illite	Chlorite	Quartz	—	Feldspar
	43—49	Illite	Chlorite	Quartz	—	Feldspar
II. Eastern uplands	0—18	Illite	—	Quartz	—	—
	18—46	—	Illite	Quartz	—	—
	46—58	—	—	Quartz	Illite	—
	58—79	Illite	—	Quartz	—	—
	79—97	Illite	—	Quartz	Chlorite	—
	97—127	Illite	—	Quartz	—	—
127—168	Illite	—	Quartz	Chlorite	—	
III. Central lowlands	0—31	—	Illite	Quartz	—	—
	31—61	Illite	—	Quartz	Chlorite	—
	61—80	—	Illite	Quartz	Chlorite	—
	80—104	Illite	Chlorite	Quartz	—	Feldspar
	104—136	Illite	Chlorite	Quartz	—	Feldspar
	136—152	Illite	Chlorite	Quartz	—	Feldspar
152—183	—	Illite	Quartz	Chlorite	Feldspar	
IV. Western uplands	0—31	—	Illite	Quartz	Chlorite	—
	31—64	—	Illite	Quartz	Chlorite	—
	64—97	Illite	—	Quartz	Chlorite	—
	97—149	Illite	—	Quartz	Chlorite	Feldspar
	149—183	Illite	—	Quartz	—	Feldspar
V. Yamuna Khadir	0—31	Illite	—	Quartz	Chlorite	Feldspar
	31—59	Illite	—	Quartz	Chlorite	—
	59—95	Illite	—	Quartz	Chlorite	Feldspar
	95—122	Illite	—	Quartz	Chlorite	Feldspar
VI. Trans Yamuna Khadir	0—33	—	Illite	Quartz	—	—
	33—59	Illite	—	Quartz	Chlorite	Feldspar
	59—102	Illite	Quartz	—	Chlorite	Feldspar
	102—147	—	Illite	Quartz	Chlorite	Feldspar

occurring in minor amounts such as quartz, feldspar and chlorite are listed in the last three columns (columns 3 to 5). There was a general tendency for the proportion of illite to increase with the depth of the profiles. There was complete absence of feldspar in type II soils.

The results of X-ray analysis found confirmation from the results of chemical analysis of the clay fractions of the soils.

The percentages of SiO_2 , Fe_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 did not show abnormal variations in different clays. The percentage of K_2O varied from 2.70 to 4.58. The high potash content⁵ was indicative of the presence of illite as the dominant clay mineral in almost all the profiles. Except in some layers of profile II, the magnesia content⁶ was also high which suggested the presence of montmorillonite or chlorite in the soils. The low values of cation exchange capacity (8 to 30 meq/100 g clay), however, ruled out the presence of any large amounts of montmorillonite and could be attributed to the illitic minerals. This fact found confirmation in silica to sesquioxide ratios which varied from 2.54 to 5.6 (except in the upper layer of profile II where it was 7.95). The silica alumina ratios⁷ further confirmed the presence of chlorite and illite in the different profiles. The trend of the molar ratios of different profiles at varying depths pointed to the presence of almost the same type of clay minerals in the different soils of Aligarh district though their proportion varied. From the results of X-ray and chemical analyses it was apparent that the clay minerals were associated with an appreciable amount of non-clay mineral matter.

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Azo Dyes. Part IV. 1-Isonicotinoyl-3-methyl-4-substituted-phenylazo-5-pyrazolones

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IN continuation with our interest in this series of compounds few more ethyl α -substituted phenylazo acetoacetates and 1-isonicotinoyl 3-methyl 4-substituted phenylazo 5-pyrazolone dyes have been prepared (column 2, table 1), and tinctorial properties of pyrazolone dyes on wool, silk, acetate silk, terylene, and nylon fabrics were investigated as per methods described earlier¹. The shades of the dyes

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TABLE I—ETHYL α -SUBSTITUTED-PHENYLAZO ACETOACETATE AND 1-ISONICOTINOYL 3-METHYL 4-SUBSTITUTED-PHENYLAZO 5-PYRAZOLONE DYES

(Analytical data, R_f -values and fungicidal properties)

No.	Compound ⁺⁺	Colour	m.p. [°]	yeild %	R_f -values		Amt. in millimoles for complete inhibition
					EO ₂ H : H ₂ O 8 : 2	BuOH:AcOH:H ₂ O 8 : 2 : 5	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1.	C ₆ H ₅ -R ^{**}	light yellow	85-6	92	0.89	0.95	—
2.	2,Cl, C ₆ H ₄ -R	yellow	65-6	80	0.90	0.94	—
3.	3,Cl, C ₆ H ₄ -R	yellow	85	76	0.91	0.95	—
4.	4,Cl, C ₆ H ₄ -R	yellow	82	91	0.91	0.95	—
5.	3,Cl, 2,CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₃ -R	yellow	87	90	0.92	0.95	—
6.	5,Cl, 2,CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₃ -R	dirty yellow	125	87	0.91	0.95	—
7.	2,3,Cl ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R	light yellow	84	98	0.86	0.92	—
8.	2,4,Cl ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R	deep yellow	132	84	0.85	0.91	—
9.	2,5,Cl ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R	light yellow	122	81	0.91	0.91	—
10.	2,6,Cl ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R	dirty yellow	82-3	79	0.91	0.91	—
11.	3,4,Cl ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R	orange yellow	96	81	0.90	0.90	—
12.	2,CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄ -R	yellow	58	80	0.93	0.85	—
13.	3,CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄ -R	yellowish orange	59	79	0.95	0.89	—
14.	4,CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄ -R	light yellow	83	92	0.93	0.91	—
15.	2,CH ₃ , 4,NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ -R	yellow	148-9	86	0.86	0.98	—